

SPECTROSCOPIC CHARACTERIZATION OF LIQUID CRYSTALLINE COMPOUNDS WITH DISPERSED Fe_3O_4 NANOPARTICLES AND THEIR IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

The synthesis involved incorporating Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles at concentrations of 0.5wt% and 1wt% into liquid crystalline compounds, specifically p-decyloxy benzoic acid (10OBA) and p-undecyloxy benzoic acid (11OBA). The resulting samples underwent comprehensive characterization through various spectroscopic techniques, including X-ray diffraction (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). To assess the textural properties of the synthesized compounds, Polarizing Optical Microscopy (POM) was employed in combination with a hot stage and camera. The findings revealed that the introduction of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles into both 10OBA and 11OBA led to the formation of nematic (NC) phases, similar to the pure 10OBA and 11OBA, albeit with a decrease in the clearing temperature, as anticipated. Additionally, the presence of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles extended the nematic thermal range in both 10OBA and 11OBA.

Keywords: Synthesis, POM, DSC, Nano-dispersion, XRD, FTIR and SEM.

INTRODUCTION

Liquid crystals are a class of functional soft materials known for their unique combination of molecular, supra-molecular, and macroscopic order and mobility. They exhibit remarkable characteristics such as long-range order, cooperative behavior, and anisotropic optical and electronic properties due to their ability to self-organize within specific temperature ranges while maintaining fluidity. These features make liquid crystals highly attractive for various applications in nanoscience and nanotechnology. When nanomaterials are introduced into liquid crystals, they can effectively control and organize the arrangement of liquid crystal molecules to achieve different phase transitions under optimal conditions. Importantly, nanoscale particles do not significantly distort the liquid crystal phases, making them suitable for enhancing the physical properties of liquid crystals.

Additionally, liquid crystals can act as tunable solvents for dispersing nanomaterials. Their anisotropic nature makes them excellent platforms for the self-assembly of nanomaterials into well-defined, organized structures in multiple dimensions. This property enables the efficient organization of various types of nanomaterials into functional superstructures. Within liquid crystals, embedded nanomaterials can trap ions, reducing ion concentration and electrical conductivity while improving the electro-optical response. One area of research focuses on the impact of iron oxide nanoparticles on ferroelectric liquid crystals, particularly their optical texture, electro-optic properties, and dielectric properties concerning temperature and electrical bias conditions.

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The incorporation of these nanoparticles leads to enhanced display parameters. The unique characteristics of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles have sparked interest across various fields, including magnetic recording media, medical applications such as drug delivery systems, hyperthermia, imaging, diagnostics, and cancer therapy, as well as in devices like sensors and catalysis. In this study, Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles were dispersed in liquid crystals, and their effects were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The influence of these nanoparticles on the thermal properties of the liquid crystals was investigated through polarizing optical microscopy (POM) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).

EXPERIMENTAL

LC compounds such as 10OBA and 11OBA and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are brought from Sigma-Aldrich laboratories, USA and used as such. For uniform dispersion of nanoparticles in 10OBA and 11OBA, the nanoparticles are first dissolved in ethyl alcohol, stirred well about 45 minutes and later introduced in the isotropic state of mesogenic material (10OBA/11OBA) in the ratio of 0.5wt% and 1 wt% concentration separately. After cooling, the nanocomposite 10OBA and 11OBA is subjected to study of the textural and phase transition temperatures using a polarizing optical microscope (SDTECHS make) with a hot stage in which the substance was filled in planar arrangement in 4 μm cells and these could be placed along with the thermometer described by Gray. Textural and phase transition temperatures are studied after preparation of the sample and observations are made again to understand the stability of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles. A DSC (Perkin Elmer Diamond DSC) is used to obtain the transition temperatures and the enthalpy values. BRUKER-ALPHA FTIR spectrometer is used for the present study. The presence of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles in 10OBA and 11OBA are studied by SEM data and existence as well as grain size is determined by XRD technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phase transition temperatures and phase sequence of the compounds has been presented by POM and confirmed by DSC. The existence of dispersed nanoparticles and their size determined by FTIR, XRD and SEM techniques.

Polarizing Microscope Studies

The transition temperatures and textures observed by POM in pure 10OBA is shown in Fig.-1a, Fig.-1b and Fig.-1c while that of 11OBA pure is shown in Fig.-2a, Fig.-2b and Fig.-2c while that of 11OBA with dispersed 0.5wt% of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles shown in Fig.-3a, Fig.-3b and Fig.-3c respectively. The thermal ranges of nematic and Smectic phases are changed slightly due to the dispersion of nanoparticles and the textures of the phase's changes by the self-assembly of nanoparticles. Thermal nematic ranges are increased with increase of concentration of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles in pure LCs. The thermal analysis studies performed from the technique such as DSC provides data regarding the temperatures, heats of transition and heat capacities of different phases. DSC reveals the presence of phase transitions in a material by detecting the enthalpy change associated with each phase transition, precise phase identifications cannot be made. The level of enthalpy change involved at the phase transition does provide some indication of the types of phase involved. DSC is used in conjunction with optical polarizing microscopy to determine the mesophase types exhibited by a material.

Thermograms of 10OBA and 11OBA with 0.5 wt % and 1 wt % Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles dispersion are shown in Fig.-4, Fig.-5 and Fig.-6. From the DSC thermogram with the dispersion of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, it is observed that the enthalpy change decreases at every phase transition when compared with the pure LC. This occurs due to the presence of the Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles with the interaction of LC molecules.

POM Textures of 10OBA Pure

(a.) Nematic at 138.9 °C

(b.) Smectic c at 122.8 °C
Fig.-1

(c.) Solid at 85.5 °C

POM Textures of 11OBA Pure

(a.) Nematic marble at 137.4 °C

(b.) Smectic c at 126.3 °C
Fig.-2

(c.) Solid at 85.4 °C

POM Textures of 11OBA + 0.5% Fe_3O_4

(a.) Nematic at 135.0 °C

(b.) Smectic c at 122.2 °C
Fig.-3

(c.) Solid at 80.5 °C

Fig.-4: DSC Thermogram of 10OBA pure and 10OBA+ 1wt% Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles

Fig.-5: DSC Thermogram of 11OBA pure and 11OBA+ 0.5wt% Fe₃O₄

Fig.-6: DSC Thermogram of 11OBA pure & 11OBA + 1wt% Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles

FTIR Studies

As synthesized Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles dispersed in 11OBA Compound is analysed by using FTIR at room temperature. The compound is stable at room temperature, the IR frequencies in solid state which are correlated in bond with the pure bond 11OBA. The assigned bonds corresponding to the resultant frequencies from the spectra are tabulated. Due to the excitation of both molecular vibrations and rotations absorptions of electromagnetic radiation causes the formation of absorption bands in the IR spectra which are useful to explain the bonding interaction of the molecules.

Fig.-7: FTIR analysis of 11OBA with 0.5 wt % Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles

The FTIR spectra as in Fig -7 shows the following bands for 11OBA and 11OBA doped with 0.5 wt % Fe_3O_4 . A band at 2917 cm^{-1} , 2849 cm^{-1} and 2917 cm^{-1} , 2848 cm^{-1} (O-H stretching), 1740 cm^{-1} and 1740 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1606 cm^{-1} and 1605 cm^{-1} (quinoid C=C stretching), 1512 cm^{-1} and 1511 cm^{-1} (benzenoid C=C stretching), 1466 cm^{-1} and 1466 cm^{-1} (stretching of aromatic ring), 1430 cm^{-1} and 1428 cm^{-1} (dimer), 1373 cm^{-1} and 1373 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching), 1166 cm^{-1} and 1168 cm^{-1} (CH-OH bending), 1128 cm^{-1} , 1063 cm^{-1} and 1128 cm^{-1} and 1063 cm^{-1} (aromatic C-H in plane bending), 843 cm^{-1} , 770 cm^{-1} and 843 cm^{-1} , 770 cm^{-1} (C-H out of plane bending) 649 cm^{-1} and 647 cm^{-1} confirms the existence of OH bond. The transmittance of radiation has decreased in case of LC dispersed with Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles. The transmittance at peak 984 cm^{-1} has decreased indicates the presence of metal oxygen vibration mode.

SEM Studies

A small amount of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles dispersed LC compounds are taken on sample holder for the scanning electron microscopy. The SEM provides the investigator with a highly magnified image of the surface of a material as the present sample contains electrons; which are needed for getting SEM image. The resolution of the SEM can approach a few nm and it can operate at magnifications that are easily adjusted from about $10\times$ - $300,000\times$. SEM gives not only topographical information but also gives the information regarding the composition of the elements in the material. To characterize the hypothesis of the size and shape of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, SEM was performed and it was shown in Fig. 8. The presence and composition

of nanoparticles in the compound is be confirmed from Energy-Dispersive Xray analysis (EDS) and shown in Fig.-9.EDS data elucidates the presence of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles in the compound is well established.

Fig.-8:EDS data of 11OBA+0.5wt% Fe₃O₄ Fig.- 9 :SEM analysis of 11OBA+0.5wt% Fe₃O₄

Element	Weight%	Atomic%
C K	79.90	83.89
O K	20.57	16.21
Fe L	-0.47	-0.11

Fig.-10: XRD Analysis of 10OBA + 1wt%Fe₃O₄

XRD Studies

The XRD data of 10OBA pure and with 1wt% Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are shown in Fig.-10 in comparison of JCPDF data peaks are well resolved and are matched with JCPDF card no. 01-089-0951 which is clearly evidenced the existence of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles. By using Scherrer's Formula, $t = k\lambda / \beta \cos\theta$, grain size is found to be 47nm, $\Lambda=1.54 \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = \text{FWHM}$, Peaks at 29.57°, 35.26°, 42.55°, 56.29°, 61.95° and 64.95° resembles the existence of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles which is matching with the early reporting.

Image Enhancement Studies

Image enhancement techniques bring out the detail in an image that is obscured or highlight certain features of interest in an image. Enhancement techniques include contrast adjustment, filtering, morphological filtering and deblurring. Image enhancement operations typically return a modified version of the original image and are frequently used as a pre-processing step to improve the results of image analysis techniques. In this work adaptive histogram equalization is used to enhance the image quality (Fig.-11 to Fig.-14).

Fig.-11: Pure 10OBA nematic image and enhanced image by adaptive histogram equalization

Fig.- 12: Pure 10OBA smectic-c image and enhanced image by adaptive histogram equalization

Fig.- 13: Pure 10OBA smectic-c- Solid image and enhanced image by adaptive histogram equalization

Fig.- 14: Pure 10OBA solid at 85.5°C image and enhanced image by adaptive histogram equalization

Adaptive histogram equalization (AHE) improves on this by transforming each pixel with a transformation function derived from a neighbourhood region. This image enhancement is an additional work which we carried to have a clear picture on the image at transition temperatures to identify the phase very easily.

CONCLUSION

The investigations conducted on the liquid crystal compounds 10OBA and 11OBA with dispersed Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles revealed that the transition temperatures determined using polarizing optical microscopy (POM) with a hot stage closely matched those obtained from differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), with any slight disparities likely stemming from variations in experimental conditions. Notably, the presence of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles led to a slight expansion of the nematic thermal ranges. Furthermore, Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) analysis indicated a reduction in the intensity of 11OBA with Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles dispersed within it. This decrease in intensity was attributed to alterations in dipole moments during molecular vibrations. Vibrations resulting in only minor changes in dipole moments produced less intense absorption compared to those causing more substantial changes. The presence of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles was confirmed through scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses. These studies demonstrated that the orientation changes induced by nanoparticle dispersion have the potential to modify transition temperatures and textural properties, which could be advantageous for display applications at lower temperatures. Additionally, image enhancement techniques were applied in this study to improve the clarity of images at transition temperatures.

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